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Insect larvae as alternative protein sources – expression of storage protein genes in non-diapausing larvae of the European corn borer *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hbn.)

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The European corn borer (ECB), a pest insect species, has the potential to be utilized in cellular agriculture as a beneficial resource due to its high larval protein content. Insect storage proteins, high molecular mass hexamers serving as amino acid depots, could be an alternative to animal-derived proteins used in cultivated meat bioprocesses. To identify the developmental stage of non-diapausing ECB larvae that would yield the highest amount of storage proteins necessary for downstream analyses, we analyzed the relative expression of genes encoding the arylphorin subunit (*aryl*) and two other storage proteins (*store1* and *store2*), normalized to actin (*act*) and ribosomal protein S3 (*rps3*) as housekeeping genes. Total RNA was isolated from whole-body homogenates of non-diapausing 2nd/3rd, 4th, and 5th instar larvae, followed by cDNA synthesis. Finally, the relative gene expression of *store1*, *store2*, and *aryl* genes at different stages of ECB active larval development was analyzed, and the results were subjected to statistical analysis (ANOVA). The expression of *store1* and *store2* genes increases throughout larval development, with peak expression observed in 5th instar larvae. The expression of *aryl*, on the other hand, was consistently high throughout active larval development, particularly during the 4th instar, likely since individual storage protein subunits need to be synthesized in sufficient amounts to successfully arrange themselves into mature proteins. The obtained results are expected considering that non-diapausing larvae grow rapidly, feed intensively, and synthesize ever-increasing amounts of storage proteins, necessary for pupal development.

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